

Extended Standardmodel

$$ESM = SU(5)_s \times SU(3)_c \times SU(2)_L \times U(1)_y \times E(1)_g$$

s...sense charges

c...color charges

L...isospin

y...hypercharge

g...gravitation

E(1)...Euclidian group

by Mag.rer.nat.Kronberger Reinhard

Email : support@kro4pro.com

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"Everything should be made as simple as possible, but not simpler."

Albert Einstein

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Introduction :

This symmetries arises by the symmetries of the coxeter element of the affine group E9 which is the affine one point extension of the well known exceptional group E8.

Why do we consider the E9 group (more specifically the Coxeter element of this group)?

1) E9 is an affine group and thus has something to do with extension.

2) The extension is flat as the universe.

3) The action of the Coxeter elements of the group produces symmetries involving our current standard model.

The fundamentals here :

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Coxeter_group

<https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wurzelsystem>

<http://home.mathematik.uni-freiburg.de/soergel/Skripten/XXSPIEG.pdf>

<https://arxiv.org/abs/1312.7777> Example 11.8

Dynkin Diagram E9 (affine one point extension of group E8) :

$\tilde{E}_9$

Derivative of the symmetries of ESM from the invariants of the Coxeter elements E9.

A Coxeter element is a product of the generating reflections of E9.

For example : Coxeter element = e1.e2.e3.e4.e5.e6.e7.e8.e9

The Coxeter polynomial is the characteristic polynomial of Coxeter elements and has the form :

$$E_9(x) = \frac{x^5 - 1}{x - 1} \cdot \frac{x^3 - 1}{x - 1} \cdot \frac{x^2 - 1}{x - 1} \cdot (x - 1)^2$$

$$E_9CS = SU(5) \times SU(3) \times SU(2) \times U(1) \times E(1)$$

$E_9(x)$... characteristic polynomial of the coxeter element of E9

$E_9(x)$ is a polynomial with terms of cyclotomic factors $Z_n = \frac{x^n - 1}{x - 1}$ for $n > 1$ and $(x - 1)$ for $n = 1$.

The cyclotomic factors are the characteristic polynomial of the A_{n-1} which is the Dynkin diagram for the $SU(n)$ Liegroup.

See more here : <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Specialunitarygroup>.

So finally the symmetry space by the actions of the Coxeter elements is

details see <https://arxiv.org/abs/1312.7781>

A visualisation for more intuitive understanding you can see at the end of the document in APPENDIX I

Compact :

Lie - group	Coxeter - Weyl	name	count bosons
$SU(5)$	$\simeq A_4$	Gloomons	$5^2 - 1 = 20 + 4 = 24$
$SU(3)$	$\simeq A_2$	Gluons	$3^2 - 1 = 6 + 2 = 8$
$SU(2)$	$\simeq A_1$	} $W^+, W^-, Z,$ } Photon	$2^2 - 1 = 2 + 1 = 3$
$U(1)$	$\simeq A_0$		
$E(1)$	$\parallel$	Graviton	1

See also <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1808.05090.pdf>

The action of a Coxeter element on an affine root system.

What bring us the additional symmetries?

- (1) These have the potential to describe new particles.
- (2) These have the potential to describe the space and time.
- (3) These have the potential to describe gravity.

< 1 > The Idea

We will now like to assign our relevant $SU(n)$'s to division algebras (real numbers, complex numbers, ...)

- $SU(1) \longleftrightarrow \mathbb{R}$
- $SU(2) \longleftrightarrow \mathbb{C}$
- $SU(3) \longleftrightarrow \mathbb{H}$
- $SU(5) \longleftrightarrow \mathbb{O}$

This 4 division algebras can be generated by the doubling process
 (see more at <https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Verdopplungsverfahren>).
 Considering the rank of the $SU(2) = 1, SU(3) = 2, SU(5) = 4$ then this is double as well.
 There appears to be a connection between the division algebras and the $SU(n)$ ($n = 2, 3, 5$).

The connections are the rank (maximal torus) of the $SU(n)$ and the orthogonal complex subspaces of the division algebra.

For example the quaternions have two orthogonal complex subspaces
 $a + b.i1$ and $c.i2 + d.i3$ (a, b, c, d real).

The $SU(3)$ has also 2 neutral elements (toris).

With this assignment we can create backgroundfields to the $SU(3)$ and $SU(5)$ like it is the higgsfield for $SU(2)$.

- $SU(1) \leftrightarrow \mathbb{R}^1$ real singulet
- $SU(2) \leftrightarrow \mathbb{C}^2$ complex dublet higgsfield
- $SU(3) \leftrightarrow \mathbb{H}^3$ quaternionic triplet
- $SU(5) \leftrightarrow \mathbb{O}^5$ octonionic quintet Octoquintenfield

Therefore, we rely analogously on the Higgsfield ($2 \times \text{complex} = \text{dublet}$).

$$\phi = \begin{bmatrix} \phi^+ \\ \phi^0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \phi_1^+ + i.\phi_2^+ \\ \phi_1^0 + i.\phi_2^0 \end{bmatrix}$$

< 2 > the Octoquintenfield ($5 \times \text{Octonions} = \text{Quintet}$).

$$\phi = \begin{bmatrix} \phi^G \\ \phi^R \\ \phi^F \\ \phi^S \\ \phi^O \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \phi_0^G + i_1.\phi_1^G + i_2.\phi_2^G + i_3.\phi_3^G + i_4.\phi_4^G + i_5.\phi_5^G + i_6.\phi_6^G + i_7.\phi_7^G \\ \phi_0^R + i_1.\phi_1^R + i_2.\phi_2^R + i_3.\phi_3^R + i_4.\phi_4^R + i_5.\phi_5^R + i_6.\phi_6^R + i_7.\phi_7^R \\ \phi_0^F + i_1.\phi_1^F + i_2.\phi_2^F + i_3.\phi_3^F + i_4.\phi_4^F + i_5.\phi_5^F + i_6.\phi_6^F + i_7.\phi_7^F \\ \phi_0^S + i_1.\phi_1^S + i_2.\phi_2^S + i_3.\phi_3^S + i_4.\phi_4^S + i_5.\phi_5^S + i_6.\phi_6^S + i_7.\phi_7^S \\ \phi_0^O + i_1.\phi_1^O + i_2.\phi_2^O + i_3.\phi_3^O + i_4.\phi_4^O + i_5.\phi_5^O + i_6.\phi_6^O + i_7.\phi_7^O \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\phi_i^O = \phi_{i1}^O + i.\phi_{i2}^O \in \mathbb{C} \quad \text{for } i = 0, 1, 2, 3$$

$$\phi_0^G, \phi_1^R, \phi_2^F, \phi_3^S \in \mathbb{C} \quad \text{else } \phi \in \mathbb{R}$$

This provides 48 degrees of freedom.
 24 of which will be "spent" for our $SU(5)$ bosons for the 5th longitudinal spin degree of freedom
 (24 Goldstone bosons swallowed over gauge transformation) thus remain 16 + 8 left.
 The S, F, R, G and H charges are the 5 charges of the $SU(5)$ analogous to the 3 color charges of $SU(3)$ and the 2 charges (+ -) of $SU(2)$.
 The letters stand for S = See, F = Touch, R = Smell, G = Taste and H = Hear
 Calling therefore the charges of the $SU(5)$ sense charges.
 Note : These charges have (such as the color charges of quarks with color) nothing to do with the senses, but to give a name to the child for reference only.

Make the following division for the 48 field components of the Octoquinten field as a physical approach :

Similar to the Higgsfield we assign our bosons to the Octoquintenfield by the following scheme.

The numbers are the sense charges (see < 2 >).

- 5 = See
- 4 = Touch
- 3 = Smell
- 2 = Taste
- 1 = Hear

ΦG	$\bar{2}\bar{1}$	$i\bar{1}$	$i\bar{2}$	$i\bar{3}$	$\bar{2}\bar{1}$	$\bar{2}\bar{3}$	$\bar{2}\bar{4}$	$\bar{2}\bar{5}$	2
ΦR	1	$3\bar{1}$	$i\bar{2}$	$i\bar{3}$	$\bar{3}\bar{2}$	$\bar{3}\bar{1}$	$\bar{3}\bar{4}$	$\bar{3}\bar{5}$	3
ΦF	1	$i\bar{1}$	$4\bar{1}$	$i\bar{3}$	$\bar{4}\bar{2}$	$\bar{4}\bar{3}$	$\bar{4}\bar{1}$	$\bar{4}\bar{5}$	4
ΦS	1	$i\bar{1}$	$i\bar{2}$	$5\bar{1}$	$\bar{5}\bar{2}$	$\bar{5}\bar{3}$	$\bar{5}\bar{4}$	$\bar{5}\bar{1}$	5
ΦO	1	$i\bar{1}$	$i\bar{2}$	$i\bar{3}$	$i\bar{4}$	$i\bar{5}$	$i\bar{6}$	$i\bar{7}$	Charge 0

$1\bar{1} - 2\bar{2}$ aso.

< 2.1 > Octoquintenfield OQF and the symmetric group (permutationgroup) S_{48}

We will assign every degree of freedom of the OQF (48) to a position in the permutation sorted by the charge lines S, F, R, G, O

(S = See, F = Touch, R = Smell, G = Taste, O = neutral)

$$\left(\begin{array}{cccccc} \phi_0^S & \phi_1^S & \dots & \dots & \phi_7^O \\ 1 & 2 & \dots & \dots & 48 \\ \alpha(1) & \alpha(2) & \dots & \dots & \alpha(48) \end{array} \right) \} \text{ permutation}$$

Then we have 4 blocks of 9 ϕ 's (chargelines) and one block of 12 ϕ 's (charge = zero) in sum $4 \times 9 + 1 \times 12 = 48 \phi$'s.

In our division of the OQF we have assigned every boson to a fix place which means to a fix degree of freedom ϕ .

For example the boson of type $\bar{5}\bar{2}$ is on the place ϕ_4^S .

The idea now is that every boson is a fixpoint (an invariant) of a permutation of S_{48} .

The question now is how many bosons do we have?

For example of type $\bar{5}\bar{1}$?

The answer is very simple because every permutation with a fixpoint on ϕ_4^S is a boson of type $\bar{5}\bar{1}$.

Then we have $47!$ bosons of type $\bar{5}\bar{1}$ because we can permutate all other ϕ 's.

Doing this with all types of bosons we get $24 \times 47! = \frac{48!}{2}$ bosons.

Let us say the mass of the bosons is the planckmass then we get

A total mass of :

$$M_T = \frac{48!}{2} \cdot m_{\text{planck}} \approx 6,2 \times 10^{52} \text{ kg}$$

Hint : This is near to the calculated total mass of the visible universe.

Analogous to the Higgspotential we declare a Potential on the Octoquintenfield

< 3 > Potential over the Octoquintenfield

Like the Higgspotential $V_h(\phi)$ uses the ϕ^4 - theory we use the ϕ^8 - theory for our Potential.

The simple reason is that our potential is $(\frac{E}{m^3})^2 \equiv \text{GeV}^8$ and the

Higgspotential is $\frac{E}{m^3} \equiv \text{GeV}^4$

$$V(\phi) = \gamma^2 |\phi|^2 + \mu^2 |\phi|^4 + \lambda^2 |\phi|^8 \quad \text{with } \phi \in OQF$$

$$|\phi|^2 = \phi^\dagger \cdot \phi$$

$\gamma, \lambda \in i.\mathbb{R}$ (imaginaer) and $\mu \in \mathbb{R}$

$$\gamma^2 \dots \text{momentumdensity}^2 \quad (\varrho.v)^2 = \left(\frac{kg}{m^3} \cdot \frac{m}{s}\right)^2$$

$$\mu^2 \dots \text{massdensity}^2 \quad (\varrho)^2 = \left(\frac{kg}{m^3}\right)^2$$

$$\lambda^2 \dots \text{spindensity}^2 \quad \left(\frac{\varrho}{v^2}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{\frac{kg}{m^3}}{\frac{m^2}{s^2}}\right)^2 \quad \text{Spin here is used not in the sense of Spin = action}$$

- 1) The potential $V(\phi)$ should be symmetric so it should have only even powers.
- 2) It should be of order 8 because it has the dimension $\left(\frac{E}{m^3}\right)^2 \equiv GeV^8$ in natural units.
- 3) It should be zero at the origin $V(0) = 0$.
- 4) It should be zero this means a real minima value on speed is c (speed of light).
 $V(c) = 0$.

Therefore we set :

$$V(\phi) = D^2 \cdot \phi^2 \cdot (\phi^2 - A^2) \cdot (\phi^2 - B^2) \cdot (\phi^2 - C^2) \quad D^2 \dots \text{a constant}$$

As seen above the potential $V(\phi)$ has only quartic and octonionic self interactions.

Then it follows that $A^2 + B^2 + C^2 = 0$ otherwise we have a ϕ^6 - term.

One solution for this is that $A = 1.c, B = c.\sqrt{\varphi}$ and $C = c.i.\varphi$

Kepler triangle

c ...speed of light

φ ...golden ratio $\approx 1,618$

But why this special choice for A, B, C there are a lot of other choices?
The special property of this choice is that it is the "only" geometrical choice.

This means A, B, C are of the shape $q^0, q^1, q^2, \dots$ geometrical sequence.
Choosing $q = \sqrt{\varphi}$ results A, B, $-i.C$.

then

$$V(\phi) = D^2 \cdot (\varphi^3 \cdot \phi^2 \cdot c^6 - 2 \cdot \varphi^2 \cdot \phi^4 \cdot c^4 + 1 \cdot \phi^8) \quad \text{drawing out } c^8 \cdot 2 \cdot \varphi^2$$

$$V(\phi) = D^2 \cdot c^8 \cdot 2 \cdot \varphi^2 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{c^2} \cdot \frac{\varphi}{2} \phi^2 - \frac{1}{c^4} \cdot \phi^4 + \frac{1}{c^8 \cdot 2 \cdot \varphi^2} \cdot \phi^8 \right)$$

$$D^2 \cdot c^8 \cdot 2 \cdot \varphi^2 = -\tilde{D}^2 \equiv \left(\frac{E}{m^3} \right)^2 \equiv GeV^8$$

then

$$V(\phi) = \tilde{D}^2 \cdot \left(-\frac{1}{c^2} \cdot \frac{\varphi}{2} \phi^2 + \frac{1}{c^4} \cdot \phi^4 - \frac{1}{c^8 \cdot 2 \cdot \varphi^2} \cdot \phi^8 \right)$$

then by comparing the terms we get :

$$\begin{cases} \gamma^2 = -\left(\frac{E}{m^3}\right)^2 \cdot \frac{1}{c^2} \cdot \frac{\varphi}{2} \\ \mu^2 = \left(\frac{E}{m^3}\right)^2 \cdot \frac{1}{c^4} \\ \lambda^2 = -\left(\frac{E}{m^3}\right)^2 \cdot \frac{1}{c^8} \cdot \frac{1}{2 \cdot \varphi^2} \end{cases}$$

Taking the golden potential GP as a distribution it is easy to show
that the third moment the skewness on the interval $[0, c\sqrt{\varphi}]$ vanishes.

$$\int_0^{c\sqrt{\varphi}} V(\phi) \cdot \phi^3 \cdot d\phi = \int_0^{c\sqrt{\varphi}} D^2 (\varphi^3 \phi^2 c^6 - 2\varphi^2 \phi^4 c^4 + \phi^8) \cdot \phi^3 \cdot d\phi =$$

$$D^2 \left(\varphi^3 c^6 \frac{\phi^6}{6} - 2\varphi^2 c^4 \frac{\phi^8}{8} + \frac{\phi^{12}}{12} \right) \Bigg|_0^{c\sqrt{\varphi}} = D^2 c^{12} \varphi^6 \left(\frac{1}{6} - \frac{2}{8} + \frac{1}{12} \right) - 0 = 0$$

The choice of this zeropoints for our potential is the only choice which
leads to a skewness (third moment) of zero on the interval $[0, \max \text{zeropoint}]$.
So it is the only choice which makes the potential stable.

Comparing the Golden - Potential GP with the
standard relativistic energy (density) equation :

$$E^2 = p^2 \cdot c^2 + m^2 \cdot c^4 \quad p = \text{momentum}; m = \text{mass}$$

Our GP has a third term and expand the equation to

$$E^2 = p^2 \cdot c^2 + m^2 \cdot c^4 + s^2 \cdot c^8$$

we call the third term the spin - term.

< 3.1 > Einstein - Form

We want that the second part of the Golden - Potential
is our quadratic vacuumenergydensity.

$$\mu^2 \cdot |c|^4 = \left(\frac{\Lambda \cdot c^4}{8\pi G} \right)^2 = (\varrho_{\text{vacuum}} \cdot c^2)^2$$

Λ ...cosmological constant

ϱ_{vacuum} ...vacuum massdensity

then with the relation $\mu^2 = \left(\frac{E}{m^3} \right)^2 \cdot \frac{1}{c^4}$ we get the potential as

EINSTEIN - FORM

$$V(\phi) = \left(\frac{\Lambda \cdot c^4}{8\pi G} \right)^2 \cdot \left(-\frac{\varphi}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{|\phi|}{c} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{|\phi|}{c} \right)^4 - \frac{1}{2 \cdot \varphi^2} \cdot \left(\frac{|\phi|}{c} \right)^8 \right)$$

We have 3 spheres where the potential vanishes.

sphere S_0 : $\{\phi \mid \text{with } |\phi| = 0\}$

sphere S_c : $\{\phi \mid \text{with } |\phi| = c\}$

sphere $S_{c\sqrt{\varphi}}$: $\{\phi \mid \text{with } |\phi| = c\sqrt{\varphi}\}$

< 3.3 > Planck – Form

With the relation

$$P_p \cdot l_p^2 = \frac{c^4}{G}$$

we get from the Einstein – Form the Planck – Form of the GP.

$$V(\phi) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{P_p}{2\pi}\right)^2 \cdot \left(\frac{\Lambda \cdot l_p^2 \cdot \varphi}{4}\right)^2 \cdot \left(- \left| \frac{\phi}{c\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^2 + 2 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{c\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^4 - \left| \frac{\phi}{c\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^8 \right)$$

where

$$P_p = \frac{c^7}{\hbar \cdot G^2} \quad \text{Planckpressure}$$

$$l_p^2 = \frac{\hbar \cdot G}{c^3} \quad \text{Plancklength}^2$$

$$\Lambda \cdot l_p^2 \approx \frac{2,6}{10^{122}} \approx \frac{4}{48!^2} \quad \text{dimensionless}$$

This assumption $\approx \rightarrow =$ is backcalculated from the Combinatorial – Form of the Golden – Potential GP which you can see later in this document.

On the combinatorial form the normalization factor N is very easy to explain and it leads to this assumption by going backward to the Planck – Form of the Golden – Potential GP

if $\Lambda \cdot l_p^2 \stackrel{\downarrow}{=} \frac{4}{48!^2}$ then we can interpret

$$N = \frac{\sqrt{\varphi}}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{48!} \quad \text{as normalization factor}$$

then our potential has the form

PLANCK – FORM

$$V(\phi) = \left(\frac{P_p}{2\pi}\right)^2 \cdot N^4 \cdot \left(- 8 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{c\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^2 + 16 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{c\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^4 - 8 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{c\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^8 \right)$$

In < 3.1 > we have defined the potential in a way so that the second term of the potential is the quadratic vacuumenergydensity on $|\phi| = c$.

Here we can see clearly that the vacuumenergydensity is :

$$\frac{P_p}{2\pi \cdot 48!^2} \quad P_p \dots \text{Planckpressure}$$

So we can say that we have such a low vacuumenergydensity because we have a lot of coordinates (48 counted) and the vacuumenergydensity comes from selfinteractions of the permutations.

For simplification we want to set $c = \hbar = G = 1$.

then the potential polynomial can be written in determinant form :

$$V(\phi) = 8 \cdot \left(\frac{\sqrt{\phi}}{2} \frac{1}{48!} \right)^4 \cdot \begin{vmatrix} 1^2 & 1^2 & 0 & \left| \frac{\phi}{\sqrt{\phi}} \right|^2 \\ 0 & \left| \frac{\phi}{\sqrt{\phi}} \right|^2 & 0 & 1^2 \\ 0 & 0 & \left| \frac{\phi}{\sqrt{\phi}} \right|^2 & 0 \\ \left| \frac{\phi}{\sqrt{\phi}} \right|^2 & 1^2 & 0 & 1^2 \end{vmatrix}$$

with $\phi \in \mathbb{O}^6$

On this form we can see why the normalization factor has fourth power (4×4 matrix),

why $\frac{1}{48!}$

the Octonion field has 48 (ϕ 's) degrees of freedom.

For every value of $|\phi|^2$ we can write

$$|\phi|^2 = \sum_{i=1}^{48} \phi_i^2$$

then for every permutation of the 48 degrees of freedom (coordinates) we get the same value for $|\phi|^2$.

That is why we have the factor $\frac{1}{48!}$ in the normalization factor N .

< 3.4 > Golden – Potential and the 16 – Cell (Coxeter group B_4, D_4) :

As seen above we can write the potential very simple as a product of

$V = \text{Norm factor} \times \text{Determinant}$

The Determinant is like a higher dimensional "Volume".

In our case the dimension is 4.

Don't misunderstand "Volume" as real spacetime volume.

It is similar to the Determinant in the Einstein Hilbert action.

Now we want to go TopDown and take a look on the 16 – cell C_{16} .

More details see here <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/16-cell>.

Some important known facts about the C_{16} .

1) count of cells = 16 tetrahedra

2) count of faces = 32 triangle

3) count of edges = 24

4) count of vertices = 8

5) every vertices has 6 edges

6) The Euler Characteristic of the 16 – Cell is zero :

$$\chi = k_0 - k_1 + k_2 - k_3 = \# \text{vertices} - \# \text{edges} + \# \text{faces} - \# \text{cells} = 8 - 24 + 32 - 16 = 0$$

7) The order of the automorphism group $S_2 \wr S_4$ is :

$$|\text{Aut}(C_{16})| = 2^4 \cdot 4! = 384$$

How can we compare the 16 - Cell with our Potential?

Es mentioned before our potential is like a 4 - dimensional "volume".
More exact it is a sum of 3 (4) volumes.

$$V(z) = \frac{N^4}{2} \cdot (0 \cdot z^0 - 16 \cdot z^1 + 32 \cdot z^2 - 16 \cdot z^4)$$

where $z = \left| \frac{\phi}{\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^2$ and
 $c = G = h = 1$

To make the potential zero we set $z = 1$ or equivalent $\phi = \sqrt{\varphi}$

$$V(1) = \frac{N^4}{2} \cdot (0 \cdot 1^0 - 16 \cdot 1^1 + 32 \cdot 1^2 - 16 \cdot 1^4) = 0 \text{ and compare it with}$$

$$\chi = k_0 - k_1 + k_2 - k_3 = 8 - 24 + 32 - 16 = 0 \text{ Euler - Characteristic}$$

we can see that both formulars alternate
and if we draw out 16 we get for the potential

$$V(1) = N^4 \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cdot (-16 \cdot 1^1 + 32 \cdot 1^2 - 16 \cdot 1^4)$$

We have two disagreements

1) we have no vertices in the potential.
The vertices are added to the edges!

2) The power of the 1 which should be the dimension of the object
does fit for the edges and the faces but not for the cells!

to 1)

How can we annihilate the vertices?

Answer : we replace it by a loop (string) and get a closed edge.

We can interpret this loops as particles.

or

to 2)
 the cells can be easily extended to fourth dimension on a convex graph.
 2 – dimension example :

So finally the potential shows 1 – dimensional , 2 – dimensional and 4 – dimensional stimulated objects.

Interpretation :

1 – dimension objects are particles
 We have two types of 1 – dimensional object.
 Closed and open ones.

$$\begin{array}{ccc} 8 - 24 & + 32 & - 16 \\ \text{edges} & \text{faces} & \text{cells} \end{array}$$

$$V(1) = N^4 \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cdot (-16 \cdot 1^1 + 32 \cdot 1^2 - 16 \cdot 1^4)$$

With the other zeropoint ($\phi = c$) we can create the same particlegraph C_{16} .

z then is $\frac{1}{\phi}$

$$V(z) = V\left(\frac{1}{\phi}\right) = N^4 \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left(-16 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\phi}\right)^1 + 32 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\phi}\right)^2 - 16 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\phi}\right)^4\right)$$

< 3.5 > Combinatorial – Form

We have the strange factor $\frac{1}{2}$ in front of the bracket.
 How can we interpret this factor?

We can draw this factor inside the brackets and set finally

$$N = \frac{\sqrt{\phi}}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{48!} \quad \text{then we get finally the}$$

COMBINATORIAL – FORM

$$V(\phi) = N^4 \cdot \left(-8 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{\sqrt{\phi}} \right|^2 + 16 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{\sqrt{\phi}} \right|^4 - 8 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{\sqrt{\phi}} \right|^8 \right)$$

for the potential.

In mathematics this is called a generating function.

2) the red **8** (edges).

As seen above the 8 comes from $-8 = 4 - 12$.

4 particles in the diagonal ↘
 12 particles ↗ zero curvature tensor

3) the blue **16** (faces).

This is the count of the $16 = 4 + 2.6$ fields of the first curvature tensor
 ($\approx$ metric tensor). ↘ in the diagonal

4) the green **8** (cells).

This is the count of the $8 = 2 + 2.3$ fields of the second curvature tensor
 ($\approx$ spin metric tensor). ↘ in the diagonal
 Details to this curvature tensors see later.

Some analytics on the Golden – Potential

without absolute values and $\phi \in \mathbb{C}$ see $\langle 8 \rangle$

$$V(\phi) = N^4 \cdot \left(-8 \cdot \left(\frac{\phi}{\sqrt{\phi}}\right)^2 + 16 \cdot \left(\frac{\phi}{\sqrt{\phi}}\right)^4 - 8 \cdot \left(\frac{\phi}{\sqrt{\phi}}\right)^8 \right) \quad N = \frac{\sqrt{\phi}}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{48!}$$

Zeropoints	momentum density ²	mass density ²	spin density ²	$\times \frac{1}{48!^4}$
0	0	0	0	$\sum = 0$
± 1	$-\frac{\phi}{2}$	1	$-\frac{1}{2\phi^2}$	$\sum = 0$
$\pm \sqrt{\phi}$	$-\frac{\phi^2}{2}$	ϕ^2	$-\frac{\phi^2}{2}$	$\sum = 0$
$\pm i\phi$	$\frac{\phi^3}{2}$	ϕ^4	$-\frac{\phi^6}{2}$	$\sum = 0$
quadratic sum = 0 $-\phi^2 + \phi + 1$	$\sum = 0$	$\sum = 4\phi^2$	$\sum = -4\phi^2$	$\sum = 0$

Some possible deductions by $\Lambda \cdot l_p^2 = \frac{4}{48!^2}$

We want write it this way $\left(\frac{48!}{2}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{l_\Lambda}{2 \cdot l_p}\right)^2 = \frac{l_\Lambda^2}{4 \cdot l_p^2}$ with $l_\Lambda = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\Lambda}}$

1) Entropy in the universe = $48!^2$ UOE

We know from Bekenstein Hawking that $4 \cdot l_p^2$ is one unit of entropy short UOE.
 Setting $c = \hbar = G = 1$ then $l_p = 1$ then

$$\frac{48!^2}{4} = \frac{l_\Lambda^2}{4} \quad \text{then} \quad S_{\text{universe}} = l_\Lambda^2 = 48!^2 \approx 1,541 \times 10^{122}$$

is the count of Entropy in the universe.

Later in $\langle 6.1 \rangle$ we will see that l_Λ belongs to a double Clifford – Torus.

We can use this 2 – dimensional flat object as the Entropy object for the universe.

This object can give an answer to the holographical – principle.

$$2) \text{Mass in the universe} = \frac{48!}{2} \cdot m_p$$

thinking that the universe is like a black hole we get by the Bekenstein Hawking Entropy and $c = \hbar = G = k = 1$:

$$S_{\text{universe}} = (2 \cdot M_{\text{universe}})^2 \quad S \dots \text{Entropy, } M \dots \text{Mass}$$

Then with the result above it follows that :

$$M_{\text{universe}} = \frac{48!}{2} \cdot m_p \approx 6,2 \times 10^{52} \text{ kg} \quad \text{with } m_p \dots \text{Planckmass}$$

< 4 > Lagrangedensity of the Octoquintenfield/Golden – Potential

Hint :

I do the same steps as shown in this cooking recipe for the Higgsfield.

<https://www.lsw.uni-heidelberg.de/users/mcamenzi/HDHiggs.pdf>

similar to the the higgsfield where the vacuumexpectation is

$$\phi_{\text{vac}} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ v \end{pmatrix}$$

the vacuumexpectation of the Oktoquintenfield is (green, yellow, orange, lightgray)

$$\phi_{\text{vac}} = v \cdot \begin{pmatrix} 1 + i_1 + i_2 + i_3 \\ 1 + i_1 + i_2 + i_3 \end{pmatrix} \quad \begin{array}{l} v = c \dots \text{speed of light} \\ \text{not the minimum of the potential!} \end{array}$$

i_1, i_2 and i_3 the imaginaer quaternions.

Different to the Higgsfield where the expectationvalue is on the minimum of the potential the expectationvalue for the fourvelocity is on the zeropoints (zerospheres) of the potential.

How can we motivate this?

If we take a look over the integral of the potential $V(\phi)$ then the speed of light c is the minimum.

$$\mathbb{V}(\phi) := \int_0^\phi V(v).dv^2$$

But i have to say that this must be still better motivated.

STEP 1: Lorentzinvariant Lagrangedensity for the Octoquintenfield

Hint :

It is not the Lagrangedensity as Energydensity instead it is a Lagrangedensity as Energydensity² (quadratic).

$$\mathcal{L}_\phi = (D^\mu \phi)^\dagger (D_\mu \phi) - V(\phi^\dagger \phi)$$

T_{ij}	$j \rightarrow$	Generators of the $SU(5)$				
$i \downarrow$		$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$
		$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$
		$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & -i & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -i & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & i & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{6}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$
		$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & -i & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -i & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & i & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -i & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & i & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{10}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -4 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$
		$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -i \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -i \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & i & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -i \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & i & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -i \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & i & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	

- $SU(2)$ █
- $SU(3)$ █ Generators
- $SU(5)$ █

We take a look on the symmetry

$$SU(5) \times E(1)$$

$$W^{ij} \quad B^0$$

calculate covariant derivation

$$D_\mu \phi = (\partial_\mu + \frac{i.g}{2} \cdot \tau_{ij} \cdot W_\mu^{ij} + \frac{i.g'}{2} \cdot Id^0 B_\mu^0) \cdot \phi$$

$$Id^0 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Always keep in mind that if we write W we mean W_μ or W^μ !

$$\tau_{ij} \cdot W_\mu^{ij} = \begin{pmatrix} V^{11} & W^{12} - iW^{21} & W^{13} - iW^{31} & W^{14} - iW^{41} & W^{15} - iW^{51} \\ W^{12} + iW^{21} & V^{22} & W^{23} - iW^{32} & W^{24} - iW^{42} & W^{25} - iW^{52} \\ W^{13} + iW^{31} & W^{23} + iW^{32} & V^{33} & W^{34} - iW^{43} & W^{35} - iW^{53} \\ W^{14} + iW^{41} & W^{24} + iW^{42} & W^{34} + iW^{43} & V^{44} & W^{45} - iW^{54} \\ W^{15} + iW^{51} & W^{25} + iW^{52} & W^{35} + iW^{53} & W^{45} + iW^{54} & V^{55} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$Trace(\tau_{ij} \cdot W_\mu^{ij}) = V^{11} + V^{22} + V^{33} + V^{44} + V^{55} = 0$$

$$V^{11} = W^{11} + \frac{W^{22}}{\sqrt{3}} + \frac{W^{33}}{\sqrt{6}} + \frac{W^{44}}{\sqrt{10}}$$

$$V^{22} = -W^{11} + \frac{W^{22}}{\sqrt{3}} + \frac{W^{33}}{\sqrt{6}} + \frac{W^{44}}{\sqrt{10}}$$

$$V^{33} = -2\frac{W^{22}}{\sqrt{3}} + \frac{W^{33}}{\sqrt{6}} + \frac{W^{44}}{\sqrt{10}}$$

$$V^{44} = -3\frac{W^{33}}{\sqrt{6}} + \frac{W^{44}}{\sqrt{10}}$$

$$V^{55} = -4\frac{W^{44}}{\sqrt{10}}$$

We write for $\frac{W^{12} - iW^{21}}{\sqrt{2}} =: W_-^{12}$ and for

$$\frac{W^{12} + iW^{21}}{\sqrt{2}} =: W_+^{12} \quad \text{and so on.}$$

Then

$$D_\mu \phi_{vac} = \frac{v}{2} \cdot i \cdot g \cdot \begin{pmatrix} V_{11} & \sqrt{2} W_+^{12} & \sqrt{2} W_+^{13} & \sqrt{2} W_+^{14} & \sqrt{2} W_+^{15} \\ \sqrt{2} W_+^{12} & V_{22} & \sqrt{2} W_+^{23} & \sqrt{2} W_+^{24} & \sqrt{2} W_+^{25} \\ \sqrt{2} W_+^{13} & \sqrt{2} W_+^{23} & V_{33} & \sqrt{2} W_+^{34} & \sqrt{2} W_+^{35} \\ \sqrt{2} W_+^{14} & \sqrt{2} W_+^{24} & \sqrt{2} W_+^{34} & V_{44} & \sqrt{2} W_+^{45} \\ \sqrt{2} W_+^{15} & \sqrt{2} W_+^{25} & \sqrt{2} W_+^{35} & \sqrt{2} W_+^{45} & V_{55} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 + i_1 + i_2 + i_3 \\ 1 + i_1 + i_2 + i_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$+ \frac{v}{2} \cdot i \cdot \begin{pmatrix} g' \cdot B^0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & g' \cdot B^0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & g' \cdot B^0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & g' \cdot B^0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & g' \cdot B^0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 + i_1 + i_2 + i_3 \\ 1 + i_1 + i_2 + i_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

then

$$(D^\mu \phi_{vac})^\dagger (D_\mu \phi_{vac}) = \frac{v^2}{4} \cdot \left[\begin{array}{l} 4 \cdot (g V_{11} + g' B^0)^2 + 8g^2 \cdot (W_-^{12} W_+^{12} + W_-^{13} W_+^{13} + W_-^{14} W_+^{14} + W_-^{15} W_+^{15}) \\ 4 \cdot (g V_{22} + g' B^0)^2 + 8g^2 \cdot (W_-^{12} W_+^{12} + W_-^{23} W_+^{23} + W_-^{24} W_+^{24} + W_-^{25} W_+^{25}) \\ 4 \cdot (g V_{33} + g' B^0)^2 + 8g^2 \cdot (W_-^{13} W_+^{13} + W_-^{23} W_+^{23} + W_-^{34} W_+^{34} + W_-^{35} W_+^{35}) \\ 4 \cdot (g V_{44} + g' B^0)^2 + 8g^2 \cdot (W_-^{14} W_+^{14} + W_-^{24} W_+^{24} + W_-^{34} W_+^{34} + W_-^{45} W_+^{45}) \\ 4 \cdot (g V_{55} + g' B^0)^2 + 8g^2 \cdot (W_-^{15} W_+^{15} + W_-^{25} W_+^{25} + W_-^{35} W_+^{35} + W_-^{45} W_+^{45}) \end{array} \right]$$

The red part is :

$$red = 4 \cdot g^2 \cdot V_{11}^2 + 4 \cdot g^2 \cdot V_{22}^2 + 4 \cdot g^2 \cdot V_{33}^2 + 4 \cdot g^2 \cdot V_{44}^2 + 4 \cdot g^2 \cdot V_{55}^2 + 20 \cdot g'^2 \cdot (B^0)^2 + 8 \cdot g \cdot g' \cdot (V^{11} + V^{22} + V^{33} + V^{44} + V^{55}) \cdot B^0$$

We know from above that $V^{11} + V^{22} + V^{33} + V^{44} + V^{55} = 0$ (trace) then it remains

$$red = 4 \cdot g^2 \cdot V_{11}^2 + 4 \cdot g^2 \cdot V_{22}^2 + 4 \cdot g^2 \cdot V_{33}^2 + 4 \cdot g^2 \cdot V_{44}^2 + 4 \cdot g^2 \cdot V_{55}^2 + 20 \cdot g'^2 \cdot (B^0)^2$$

Multiply out we get finally for the red part

$$red = 8g^2 \cdot (|W^{11}|^2 + |W^{22}|^2 + |W^{33}|^2 + |W^{44}|^2) + 20g'^2 \cdot |B^0|^2$$

With

$$2 \cdot W_-^{ij} \cdot W_+^{ij} = |W_-^{ij}|^2 + |W_+^{ij}|^2$$

we get the following final result :

$$(D^\mu \phi_{vac})^\dagger (D_\mu \phi_{vac}) = \frac{v^2}{4} \cdot [green\ area + red\ area]$$

$$(D^\mu \phi_{vac})^\dagger (D_\mu \phi_{vac}) = \frac{c^2}{2} \cdot [4 \cdot g^2 \cdot (|W_-^{12}|^2 + |W_+^{12}|^2 + |W_-^{13}|^2 + |W_+^{13}|^2 + |W_-^{14}|^2 + |W_+^{14}|^2 + |W_-^{15}|^2 + |W_+^{15}|^2 + |W_-^{23}|^2 + |W_+^{23}|^2 + |W_-^{24}|^2 + |W_+^{24}|^2 + |W_-^{25}|^2 + |W_+^{25}|^2 + |W_-^{34}|^2 + |W_+^{34}|^2 + |W_-^{35}|^2 + |W_+^{35}|^2 + |W_-^{45}|^2 + |W_+^{45}|^2) + 4 \cdot g^2 \cdot (|W^{11}|^2 + |W^{22}|^2 + |W^{33}|^2 + |W^{44}|^2) + 20g'^2 \cdot |B^0|^2]$$

$E(1)$ Gravitation

The W 's are the dark matter particles with Planckmass.
 B^0 is the Graviton.

< 5 > Curvaturetensors by the Octoquintenfield

The construction comes from multiplications (symmetric to the diagonal) by 2 degrees of freedom (complex subspaces).

With this construction the tensor is symmetric in the diagonal.

$$\phi = \begin{bmatrix} \phi^G \\ \phi^R \\ \phi^F \\ \phi^S \\ \phi^O \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \phi_0^G + i_1 \cdot \phi_1^G + i_2 \cdot \phi_2^G + i_3 \cdot \phi_3^G + i_4 \cdot \phi_4^G + i_5 \cdot \phi_5^G + i_6 \cdot \phi_6^G + i_7 \cdot \phi_7^G \\ \phi_0^R + i_1 \cdot \phi_1^R + i_2 \cdot \phi_2^R + i_3 \cdot \phi_3^R + i_4 \cdot \phi_4^R + i_5 \cdot \phi_5^R + i_6 \cdot \phi_6^R + i_7 \cdot \phi_7^R \\ \phi_0^F + i_1 \cdot \phi_1^F + i_2 \cdot \phi_2^F + i_3 \cdot \phi_3^F + i_4 \cdot \phi_4^F + i_5 \cdot \phi_5^F + i_6 \cdot \phi_6^F + i_7 \cdot \phi_7^F \\ \phi_0^S + i_1 \cdot \phi_1^S + i_2 \cdot \phi_2^S + i_3 \cdot \phi_3^S + i_4 \cdot \phi_4^S + i_5 \cdot \phi_5^S + i_6 \cdot \phi_6^S + i_7 \cdot \phi_7^S \\ \phi_0^O + i_1 \cdot \phi_1^O + i_2 \cdot \phi_2^O + i_3 \cdot \phi_3^O + i_4 \cdot \phi_4^O + i_5 \cdot \phi_5^O + i_6 \cdot \phi_6^O + i_7 \cdot \phi_7^O \end{bmatrix}$$

ΦG	1	i1	i2	i3	i4	i5	i6	i7	
ΦR	i1	1	i2	i3	i4	i5	i6	i7	
ΦF	i2	i1	1	i3	i4	i5	i6	i7	
ΦS	i3	i2	i1	1	i4	i5	i6	i7	
ΦO	i4	i3	i2	i1	1	i5	i6	i7	Charge 0

c...speed of light
G...Gravitationconstant
ħ...Planckconstant

symmetric curvaturetensor

$$C_{em} = \frac{c}{G \cdot \hbar} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \phi_0^O \cdot \phi_0^O & i_1 \phi_0^R \cdot \phi_1^G & i_2 \phi_0^F \cdot \phi_2^G & i_3 \phi_0^S \cdot \phi_3^G \\ i_1 \phi_1^R \cdot \phi_1^G & -\phi_1^O \cdot \phi_1^O & i_3 \phi_1^F \cdot \phi_2^R & -i_2 \phi_1^S \cdot \phi_3^R \\ i_2 \phi_2^F \cdot \phi_2^G & i_3 \phi_1^F \cdot \phi_2^R & -\phi_2^O \cdot \phi_2^O & i_1 \phi_2^S \cdot \phi_3^F \\ i_3 \phi_3^S \cdot \phi_3^G & -i_2 \phi_1^S \cdot \phi_3^R & i_1 \phi_2^S \cdot \phi_3^F & -\phi_3^O \cdot \phi_3^O \end{pmatrix}$$

This tensor is up to a constant equal to the energy – momentum tensor.

$$\frac{E_{i,j}}{m^3} = \phi_i \cdot \phi_j \cdot \frac{c}{G \cdot \hbar} \cdot \frac{c^4}{8\pi \cdot G} \quad \text{energydensity}$$

10 independent fields.

remark :

for $\phi = c$ we get as curvature the plank curvature which is the reciprocal of the plank area.

The value of the curvature is :

$$0,34 \times 10^{70} \frac{1}{m^2}$$

Second CURVATURE TENSOR from the Octoquintenfield (generates a spinpotential)

The construction comes from multiplications by 4 degrees of freedom (quaternionic subspaces).

With this construction the tensor is symmetric in both diagonals.

$$\phi = \begin{bmatrix} \phi^G \\ \phi^R \\ \phi^F \\ \phi^S \\ \phi^O \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \phi_0^G + i_1 \cdot \phi_1^G + i_2 \cdot \phi_2^G + i_3 \cdot \phi_3^G + i_4 \cdot \phi_4^G + i_5 \cdot \phi_5^G + i_6 \cdot \phi_6^G + i_7 \cdot \phi_7^G \\ \phi_0^R + i_1 \cdot \phi_1^R + i_2 \cdot \phi_2^R + i_3 \cdot \phi_3^R + i_4 \cdot \phi_4^R + i_5 \cdot \phi_5^R + i_6 \cdot \phi_6^R + i_7 \cdot \phi_7^R \\ \phi_0^F + i_1 \cdot \phi_1^F + i_2 \cdot \phi_2^F + i_3 \cdot \phi_3^F + i_4 \cdot \phi_4^F + i_5 \cdot \phi_5^F + i_6 \cdot \phi_6^F + i_7 \cdot \phi_7^F \\ \phi_0^S + i_1 \cdot \phi_1^S + i_2 \cdot \phi_2^S + i_3 \cdot \phi_3^S + i_4 \cdot \phi_4^S + i_5 \cdot \phi_5^S + i_6 \cdot \phi_6^S + i_7 \cdot \phi_7^S \\ \phi_0^O + i_1 \cdot \phi_1^O + i_2 \cdot \phi_2^O + i_3 \cdot \phi_3^O + i_4 \cdot \phi_4^O + i_5 \cdot \phi_5^O + i_6 \cdot \phi_6^O + i_7 \cdot \phi_7^O \end{bmatrix}$$

ΦG	1	i1	i2	i3	i4	i5	i6	i7	
ΦR	i1	1	i2	i3	i4	i5	i6	i7	
ΦF	i2	i1	1	i3	i4	i5	i6	i7	
ΦS	i3	i2	i1	1	i4	i5	i6	i7	
ΦO	i4	i3	i2	i1	1	i5	i6	i7	Charge 0

$$C_{spin} = \left(\frac{c}{G \cdot \hbar} \right)^2 \cdot \begin{pmatrix} -\phi_0^O \cdot \phi_0^O \cdot \phi_3^O \cdot \phi_3^O & -C & B & -A \\ -C & \phi_1^O \cdot \phi_1^O \cdot \phi_2^O \cdot \phi_2^O & -A & B \\ B & -A & \phi_1^O \cdot \phi_1^O \cdot \phi_2^O \cdot \phi_2^O & -C \\ -A & B & -C & -\phi_0^O \cdot \phi_0^O \cdot \phi_3^O \cdot \phi_3^O \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \phi_0^S \cdot \phi_3^G \cdot \phi_1^F \cdot \phi_2^R \\ B &= \phi_0^F \cdot \phi_2^G \cdot \phi_1^S \cdot \phi_3^R \\ C &= \phi_0^S \cdot \phi_1^G \cdot \phi_2^F \cdot \phi_3^R \end{aligned}$$

5 independent fields A, B, C and two in the diagonal.

< 6 > Extension of the General Relativity GR by the second curvaturetensor

The Golden – Potential GP has two symmetric curvaturetensors.

This motivates us to extend the Einstein Equation.

I think this shows that the GR (General Relativity) has to be extended

by an imaginry part (spinpart) to be a consistent quantumtheorie.

So finally we expect something like $GR+i \cdot GR^O$ where GR^O is the spinpart.

with the two curvaturetensors C_{em} and C_{spin} we can define following equation :

EGR Extended General Relativity

$$g \cdot \text{Real}(C_{em}) + g^2 \cdot \frac{i}{\varphi \sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{1}{\Lambda} \cdot C_{spin} = \frac{8 \cdot \pi \cdot G}{c^4} \cdot (T_{\mu\nu} + \frac{i}{\varphi \sqrt{2}} \cdot S_{\mu\nu})$$

where the real part is the GR and the imaginaer part is GR^O

GR...General Relativity

GR^O ...Spinextension of GR

φ ...golden ratio

Λ ...cosmological constant

l_p ...Plancklength

$$g = \begin{cases} \Lambda \cdot l_p^2 = \frac{4}{48!^2} \approx \frac{2,6}{10^{122}} & \text{for the vacuum} \\ 1 & \text{else} \end{cases}$$

Hint :

The small value of g shows the cosmological constant problem or vacuum catastrophe.

$$g = \Lambda \cdot l_p^2 = \frac{4}{48!^2} \approx \frac{2,6}{10^{122}} \quad \text{for the vacuum}$$

the operator $\text{Real}(A)$ is defined by

$$\text{Real} \left(\begin{pmatrix} a_{0,0} & i_1 \cdot a_{0,1} & i_2 \cdot a_{0,2} & i_3 \cdot a_{0,3} \\ i_1 \cdot a_{1,0} & a_{1,1} & i_3 \cdot a_{1,2} & i_2 \cdot a_{1,3} \\ i_2 \cdot a_{2,0} & i_3 \cdot a_{2,1} & a_{2,2} & i_1 \cdot a_{2,3} \\ i_3 \cdot a_{3,0} & i_2 \cdot a_{3,1} & i_1 \cdot a_{3,2} & a_{3,3} \end{pmatrix} \right) = \begin{pmatrix} a_{0,0} & a_{0,1} & a_{0,2} & a_{0,3} \\ a_{1,0} & a_{1,1} & a_{1,2} & a_{1,3} \\ a_{2,0} & a_{2,1} & a_{2,2} & a_{2,3} \\ a_{3,0} & a_{3,1} & a_{3,2} & a_{3,3} \end{pmatrix}$$

the reversing Real^{-1} is :

$$\text{Real}^{-1} \left(\begin{pmatrix} a_{0,0} & a_{0,1} & a_{0,2} & a_{0,3} \\ a_{1,0} & a_{1,1} & a_{1,2} & a_{1,3} \\ a_{2,0} & a_{2,1} & a_{2,2} & a_{2,3} \\ a_{3,0} & a_{3,1} & a_{3,2} & a_{3,3} \end{pmatrix} \right) = \begin{pmatrix} a_{0,0} & i_1 \cdot a_{0,1} & i_2 \cdot a_{0,2} & i_3 \cdot a_{0,3} \\ i_1 \cdot a_{1,0} & a_{1,1} & i_3 \cdot a_{1,2} & i_2 \cdot a_{1,3} \\ i_2 \cdot a_{2,0} & i_3 \cdot a_{2,1} & a_{2,2} & i_1 \cdot a_{2,3} \\ i_3 \cdot a_{3,0} & i_2 \cdot a_{3,1} & i_1 \cdot a_{3,2} & a_{3,3} \end{pmatrix}$$

i_1, i_2, i_3 ...imaginaer quaternions

more detailed with the two curvaturetensors of the Octoquintenfield :

$$\frac{8\pi G}{c^4} \cdot (T_{\mu\nu} + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot S_{\mu\nu}) = g \cdot \text{Real}(C_{em}) + g^2 \cdot \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{1}{\Lambda} \cdot C_{spin} =$$

$$= \frac{g \cdot c}{G \cdot \hbar} \left[\begin{pmatrix} \phi_0^0 \cdot \phi_0^0 & \phi_0^R \cdot \phi_1^G & \phi_0^F \cdot \phi_2^G & \phi_0^S \cdot \phi_3^G \\ \text{sym.} & -\phi_1^0 \cdot \phi_1^0 & \phi_1^F \cdot \phi_2^R & -\phi_1^S \cdot \phi_3^R \\ \text{sym.} & \text{sym.} & -\phi_2^0 \cdot \phi_2^0 & \phi_2^S \cdot \phi_3^F \\ \text{sym.} & \text{sym.} & \text{sym.} & -\phi_3^0 \cdot \phi_3^0 \end{pmatrix} + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{g}{\Lambda} \cdot \frac{c}{G \cdot \hbar} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} -\phi_0^0 \cdot \phi_0^0 \cdot \phi_3^0 \cdot \phi_3^0 - \phi_0^R \cdot \phi_1^G \cdot \phi_2^S \cdot \phi_3^F & \phi_0^F \cdot \phi_2^G \cdot \phi_1^S \cdot \phi_3^R - \phi_0^S \cdot \phi_3^G \cdot \phi_1^F \cdot \phi_2^R \\ \text{sym.} & \phi_1^0 \cdot \phi_1^0 \cdot \phi_2^0 \cdot \phi_2^0 - \phi_0^S \cdot \phi_3^G \cdot \phi_1^F \cdot \phi_2^R & \phi_0^F \cdot \phi_2^G \cdot \phi_1^S \cdot \phi_3^R \\ \text{sym.} & \text{sym.} & \phi_1^0 \cdot \phi_1^0 \cdot \phi_2^0 \cdot \phi_2^0 - \phi_0^R \cdot \phi_1^G \cdot \phi_2^S \cdot \phi_3^F \\ \text{sym.} & \text{sym.} & \text{sym.} & -\phi_0^0 \cdot \phi_0^0 \cdot \phi_3^0 \cdot \phi_3^0 \end{pmatrix} \right]$$

10 different independent products or fields.
generates Poincare group $\mathbb{R}^{1,3} \times O(1,3)$
5 different independent products or fields.
sym. and red products are redundant.
 $2 \times S^1 \times S^1 \times SU(2) = 2 \times \mathbb{T}^2 \times SU(2)$ with $\mathbb{T}^2 = \text{Torus}$

$\mathbb{T}^2$...Clifford – Torus
 This flat torus is a subset of the unit 3 – sphere S^3 .
 The Clifford torus divides the 3 – sphere into two congruent solid tori.
 The Clifford – Torus embedded in S^3 becomes a minimal surface.

The second curvature tensor C_{spin} is determined by the first curvature tensor C_{em} because its components are a mix of the components of C_{em} .

< 6.1 > The vacuum part of the extended Einstein equation then is :

with

$$\phi_0^0 = \phi_1^0 = \phi_2^0 = \phi_3^0 = c \quad \text{speed of light and other } \phi^i \text{ are zero and}$$

$$g = \Lambda \cdot l_p^2 \quad \text{for the vacuum}$$

then

$$\text{Vacuum Energy density} = \frac{c^4}{8\pi G} \cdot \left[\Lambda \cdot \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot \Lambda \cdot \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \right] \begin{pmatrix} \oplus \\ \ominus \\ \oplus \\ \ominus \end{pmatrix} \begin{matrix} \mathbb{T}_{\text{up}}^2 \\ \mathbb{T}_{\text{down}}^2 \end{matrix}$$

hyperbolic (1,3)
ultrahyperbolic (2,2)

generates flat expanding spacetime

$\mathbb{T}_{\Lambda^0}^2 = \begin{pmatrix} \ominus \\ -1 \\ \oplus \\ +1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} C_- \\ C_+ \end{pmatrix}$
 Spinor

generates $2 \times$ spinning Torus $\mathbb{T}_{\Lambda^0}^2 = S^1 \times S^1$
 flat Clifford – Torus

generates flat expanding and twisting vacuum

This is in accordance with the Golden – Potential GP on $\phi = c$

$$V(c) = \left(\frac{\Lambda \cdot c^4}{8\pi G} \right)^2 \cdot \frac{1}{2 \cdot \varphi^2} \cdot \left(-\varphi^3 + 2 \cdot \varphi^2 - 1 \right) = \text{Energy density}^2 = 0$$

$$\frac{8\pi G}{c^4} \cdot (T_{\mu\nu} + \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}\varphi} \cdot S_{\mu\nu}) = \Lambda \cdot \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} + \frac{i\Lambda}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

< 6.2 > Scalefactor for the accelerated expanding Universe by our assumption

To make it simple we are thinking about an universe without radiation and mass.
 This means only the vacuumenergydensity is acting.
 Then the Hubbleconstant is really constant.

$$H = \sqrt{\frac{c^2 \cdot \Lambda}{3}} = \frac{a'(t)}{a(t)} \quad \text{then}$$

$$a(t) \propto e^{H \cdot t} = e^{\sqrt{\frac{c^2 \cdot \Lambda}{3}} \cdot t}$$

$$\text{then with assumption } \Lambda \cdot l_p^2 = \frac{4}{48!^2}$$

we get finally

$$a(t) \propto e^{H \cdot t} = e^{\sqrt{\frac{4}{3}} \cdot \frac{t}{48! t_p}}$$

- a...scale factor
- Λ ...cosmological constant
- c...speed of light
- l_p ...Plancklength
- t_p ...Plancktime

< 7 > Getting a closed form for the Extended General Relativity EGR.

we know that our energy – momentum curvaturetensor

$$\text{Real}(C_{em}) = R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{R}{2} \cdot g_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda \cdot g_{\mu\nu} \quad \text{and that}$$

C_{spin} is defined by multiplication of tensorelements of C_{em}

The question now is how can we express C_{spin} analogous to C_{em} above as terms of Riemann – Geometrie?

For that we define the operator for 4×4 matrices or tensors :

Matrixoperator Tau

$$\mathcal{T} = T + \diagup + \diagdown$$

Transpose in the big diagonal from top right to bottom left. and then finally in the small diagonals.

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_{0,0} & a_{0,1} & a_{0,2} & a_{0,3} \\ a_{1,0} & a_{1,1} & a_{1,2} & a_{1,3} \\ a_{2,0} & a_{2,1} & a_{2,2} & a_{2,3} \\ a_{3,0} & a_{3,1} & a_{3,2} & a_{3,3} \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{pmatrix} a_{3,3} & a_{2,3} & a_{1,3} & a_{0,3} \\ a_{3,2} & a_{2,2} & a_{1,2} & a_{0,2} \\ a_{3,1} & a_{2,1} & a_{1,1} & a_{0,1} \\ a_{3,0} & a_{2,0} & a_{1,0} & a_{0,0} \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{pmatrix} a_{3,3} & a_{2,3} & a_{1,3} & a_{1,2} \\ a_{3,2} & a_{2,2} & a_{0,3} & a_{0,2} \\ a_{3,1} & a_{3,0} & a_{1,1} & a_{0,1} \\ a_{2,1} & a_{2,0} & a_{1,0} & a_{0,0} \end{pmatrix}$$

$A \qquad \qquad \qquad A^{\mathcal{T}}$

and a special simple matricesmultiplication
 $C = A \cdot B$
 with

$$c_{i,j} = \begin{cases} +a_{i,j} \cdot b_{i,j} & \text{if } i = j \\ -a_{i,j} \cdot b_{i,j} & \text{if } i \neq j \end{cases}$$

then it is easy to see that

$$(A + B)^{\mathcal{T}} = A^{\mathcal{T}} + B^{\mathcal{T}}$$

$$(A^{\overline{3}})^{\overline{3}} = A$$

with

$$C_{em} = \frac{c}{G \cdot \hbar} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \phi_0^0 \cdot \phi_0^0 & i_1 \cdot \phi_0^R \cdot \phi_1^G & i_2 \cdot \phi_0^F \cdot \phi_2^G & i_3 \cdot \phi_0^S \cdot \phi_3^G \\ \text{sym.} & -\phi_1^0 \cdot \phi_1^0 & i_3 \cdot \phi_1^F \cdot \phi_2^R & -i_2 \cdot \phi_1^S \cdot \phi_3^R \\ \text{sym.} & \text{sym.} & -\phi_2^0 \cdot \phi_2^0 & i_1 \cdot \phi_2^S \cdot \phi_3^F \\ \text{sym.} & \text{sym.} & \text{sym.} & -\phi_3^0 \cdot \phi_3^0 \end{pmatrix} = \frac{c}{G \cdot \hbar} \cdot V_{em}$$

and

$$C_{spin} = \left(\frac{c}{G \cdot \hbar}\right)^2 \cdot \begin{pmatrix} -\phi_0^0 \cdot \phi_0^0 \cdot \phi_3^0 \cdot \phi_3^0 - \phi_0^R \cdot \phi_1^G \cdot \phi_2^S \cdot \phi_3^F & \phi_0^F \cdot \phi_2^G \cdot \phi_1^S \cdot \phi_3^R - \phi_0^S \cdot \phi_3^G \cdot \phi_1^F \cdot \phi_2^R \\ \text{sym.} & \phi_1^0 \cdot \phi_1^0 \cdot \phi_2^0 \cdot \phi_2^0 - \phi_0^S \cdot \phi_3^G \cdot \phi_1^F \cdot \phi_2^R & \phi_0^F \cdot \phi_2^G \cdot \phi_1^S \cdot \phi_3^R \\ \text{sym.} & \text{sym.} & \phi_1^0 \cdot \phi_1^0 \cdot \phi_2^0 \cdot \phi_2^0 - \phi_0^R \cdot \phi_1^G \cdot \phi_2^S \cdot \phi_3^F \\ \text{sym.} & \text{sym.} & \text{sym.} & -\phi_0^0 \cdot \phi_0^0 \cdot \phi_3^0 \cdot \phi_3^0 \end{pmatrix} = \left(\frac{c}{G \cdot \hbar}\right)^2 \cdot V_{spin}$$

it follows that

$$C_{spin} = \text{Real}(C_{em}) \cdot \text{Real}(C_{em})^{\overline{3}}$$

with

$$\text{Real}(C_{em}) = R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{R}{2} \cdot g_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda \cdot g_{\mu\nu} = G_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda \cdot g_{\mu\nu} = K_{\mu\nu}$$

and

$$\text{Real}(C_{em}) + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{1}{\Lambda} \cdot C_{spin} = \frac{8 \cdot \pi \cdot G}{c^4} \cdot \left(T_{\mu\nu} + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot S_{\mu\nu}\right)$$

we get the final compact result for the extension of General Relativity by

EGR

$$K_{\mu\nu} + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{1}{\Lambda} \cdot K_{\mu\nu} \cdot K_{\mu\nu}^{\overline{3}} = \frac{8 \cdot \pi \cdot G}{c^4} \cdot \left(T_{\mu\nu} + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot S_{\mu\nu}\right)$$

with

$$S_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\Lambda} \cdot T_{\mu\nu} \cdot T_{\mu\nu} \dots \text{Spintensor}$$

$$K_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{R}{2} \cdot g_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda \cdot g_{\mu\nu}$$

$$K_{\mu\nu}^{\overline{3}} = R_{\mu\nu}^{\overline{3}} - \frac{R}{2} \cdot g_{\mu\nu}^{\overline{3}} + \Lambda \cdot g_{\mu\nu}^{\overline{3}}$$

$\varphi \dots$ golden ratio

The real part is the known General Relativity.

The imaginaer part is the Spinextension of GR.

Hint : The Energy–Stress tensor is still symmetric with or without Spin!

< 7.1 > Showing a combinatorial dimensionless form of the EGR

With the relation shown in < 3.5 > and Appendix III

$$\Lambda \cdot l_p^2 = \frac{4}{48!^2}$$

we can write :

$$\frac{1}{\Lambda} = l_p^2 \cdot \frac{48!^2}{4}$$

Then our formular in < 6 > can be written to :

$$\frac{8 \cdot \pi \cdot G}{c^4} \cdot \left(T_{\mu\nu} + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot S_{\mu\nu}\right) = g \cdot \text{Real}(C_{em}) + g^2 \cdot \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{1}{\Lambda} \cdot C_{spin} \quad g = \begin{cases} \Lambda \cdot l_p^2 & \text{for the vacuum} \\ 1 & \text{else} \end{cases}$$

Hint : instead of $\text{Real}(C_{em})$ we write short C_{em} and keep it in mind!

$$\frac{8 \cdot \pi \cdot G}{c^4} \cdot \left(T_{\mu\nu} + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot S_{\mu\nu}\right) = g \cdot C_{em} + g^2 \cdot \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot l_p^2 \cdot \frac{48!^2}{4} \cdot C_{spin}$$

$$\frac{8 \cdot \pi \cdot G}{c^4} \cdot (T_{\mu\nu} + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot S_{\mu\nu}) = g \cdot \frac{c}{G \cdot \hbar} \cdot V_{em} + g^2 \cdot \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot l_p^2 \cdot \frac{48!^2}{4} \cdot (\frac{c}{G \cdot \hbar})^2 \cdot V_{spin}$$

then with

$$\frac{c}{G \cdot \hbar} = \frac{1}{c^2 \cdot l_p^2}$$

$$\frac{8 \cdot \pi \cdot G}{c^4} \cdot (T_{\mu\nu} + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot S_{\mu\nu}) = g \cdot \frac{1}{c^2 \cdot l_p^2} \cdot V_{em} + g^2 \cdot \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{48!^2}{4} \cdot \frac{1}{c^4 \cdot l_p^2} \cdot V_{spin} \quad | \cdot l_p^2$$

$$\frac{8 \cdot \pi \cdot G}{c^4} \cdot l_p^2 \cdot (T_{\mu\nu} + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot S_{\mu\nu}) = g \cdot \frac{1}{c^2} \cdot V_{em} + g^2 \cdot \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{48!^2}{4} \cdot \frac{1}{c^4} \cdot V_{spin}$$

then with

$$P_p = \frac{c^7}{G^2 \cdot \hbar} \quad \text{Planckpressure and } g = 1 \text{ for not vacuum}$$

we get finally

$$\boxed{\frac{8 \cdot \pi}{P_p} \cdot (T_{\mu\nu} + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot S_{\mu\nu}) = \frac{1}{c^2} \cdot V_{em} + \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{1}{8N^2} \cdot \frac{1}{c^4} \cdot V_{spin}}$$

$$V_{em}, V_{spin} \text{ see } < 7 >$$

$$N = \frac{\sqrt{\varphi}}{2 \cdot 48!}$$

dimensionless Combinatorial – Form of the EGR

< 7.2 > Spin and possible proofing of the Extended General Relativity EGR.

As noted in < 5 > the second curvaturetensor C_{spin} is responsible for the Spin.

Obviously the C_{spin} is directly connected to the energy – momentum curvaturetensor C_{em} .

So in principle the Extended General Relativity short EGR could be proofed because the spin of a particle changes the Energy – Momentum – Tensor.

First we have to show how the spin of a particle acts on the C_{spin} .

For that we have to take a closer look on the C_{spin} .

As seen in < 5 > the structure is :

Now how can we embed dirac – fermions with spin $\frac{1}{2}$ into the EGR?

For that we want to assign the structure of the C_{spin} in the following way to fermions :

Then a resting electron excites the C_{spin} and the C_{em} as follow :

$$Spin = \frac{1}{2} \text{ Dirac: } \begin{array}{c} +\frac{1}{2} \\ \begin{array}{|c|c|c|c|} \hline \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare \\ \hline \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare \\ \hline \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare \\ \hline \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare \\ \hline \end{array} \\ -\frac{1}{2} \\ \color{red}\blacksquare \text{ excited components} \end{array} = \begin{pmatrix} -\phi_0^2, \phi_3^2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -\phi_0^2, \phi_3^2 \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{Spinor } \psi_D^G = \begin{pmatrix} (-1) \\ \bullet \\ \bullet \\ (-1) \end{pmatrix}$$

Then complete in the EGR:

$$\frac{8\pi G}{c^4} \cdot (T_{\mu\nu} + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot S_{\mu\nu}) = \frac{c}{G\hbar} \cdot \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{Minkowski} \\ \begin{array}{|c|c|c|c|} \hline \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare \\ \hline \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare \\ \hline \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare \\ \hline \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare \\ \hline \end{array} + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{1}{\Lambda} \cdot \frac{c}{G\hbar} \cdot \begin{array}{c} \text{double Torus} \\ \begin{array}{|c|c|c|c|} \hline \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare \\ \hline \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare \\ \hline \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare \\ \hline \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare \\ \hline \end{array} \end{array} \right) \begin{array}{l} \text{Spin UP} \\ \text{Spin DOWN} \end{array}$$

$$= \frac{c}{G\hbar} \cdot \left[\begin{pmatrix} \phi_0^2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -\phi_3^2 \end{pmatrix} + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{1}{\Lambda} \cdot \frac{c}{G\hbar} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} -\phi_0^2, \phi_3^2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -\phi_0^2, \phi_3^2 \end{pmatrix} \right]$$

$\color{red}\blacksquare$ excited
 φ ...golden ratio
 pressure on a random spacedirection z

This pressure to a spacedirection should be proofable in principle!

We allow $\phi \in \mathbb{C}$

< 8 > Some important points of the Golden – Potential

To get the maxima, minima and the zeropoints of the potential we have to substitute $z = \phi^2$ it is enough (because of symmetry) to take a look on the positive ϕ' s. and solve the cubic equations in the bracket

$$V(\sqrt{z}) = z \cdot (\gamma^2 + \mu^2 \cdot z + \lambda^2 \cdot z^3) \text{ and}$$

$$V'(\sqrt{z}) = \sqrt{z} \cdot (2 \cdot \gamma^2 + 4 \cdot \mu^2 \cdot z + 8 \cdot \lambda^2 \cdot z^3)$$

We will make it short and write the results.

First the Zeropoints:

$$z_1 = u + v = -\sqrt{\frac{2C}{3}} \cdot \left(\sqrt[3]{\frac{\sqrt{27} - i \cdot \sqrt{5}}{\sqrt{32}}} + \sqrt[3]{\frac{\sqrt{27} + i \cdot \sqrt{5}}{\sqrt{32}}} \right)$$

$$z_2 = \epsilon_1 \cdot u + \epsilon_2 \cdot v$$

$$z_3 = \epsilon_2 \cdot u + \epsilon_1 \cdot v$$

$$\text{Where } \epsilon_1 = -\frac{1}{2} + i \cdot \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \text{ and } \epsilon_2 = -\frac{1}{2} - i \cdot \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}$$

$C = c^4 \cdot \varphi^2$
 c ...speed of light
 φ ...golden ratio

then

$$z_1 = -0,990839414 \times 2 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{2C}{3}}$$

$$z_2 = 0,378466979 \times 2 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{2C}{3}}$$

$$z_3 = 0,612372435 \times 2 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{2C}{3}}$$

then the zeropoints are

$$\phi_1 = i \cdot 0,995409169 \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{8 \cdot C}{3}}$$

$$\phi_2 = 0,615196699 \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{8 \cdot C}{3}}$$

$$\phi_3 = 0,782542290 \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{8 \cdot C}{3}}$$

$$\boxed{\phi_1 = i.c.\varphi} = i.0,995409169 \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{8.C}{3}} = i.\sin(84,507759190) \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{8.C}{3}}$$

$$\alpha_{c.\varphi} = 84,507759190^\circ$$

$$\boxed{\phi_2 = c} = 0,615196699 \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{8.C}{3}} = \sin(37,966214178) \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{8.C}{3}}$$

$$\alpha_c = 37,966214178^\circ$$

$$\boxed{\phi_3 = c.\sqrt{\varphi}} = 0,78254229 \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{8.C}{3}} = \sin(128,506061932) \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{8.C}{3}}$$

$$\alpha_{c.\sqrt{\varphi}} = 128,506061932^\circ$$

Then the Maxima and the Minima :

$$z_1 = u + v = -\sqrt{\frac{C}{3}} \cdot \left(\sqrt[3]{\frac{\sqrt{37} - i.\sqrt{27}}{\sqrt{64}}} + \sqrt[3]{\frac{\sqrt{37} + i.\sqrt{27}}{\sqrt{64}}} \right)$$

$$z_2 = \epsilon_1.u + \epsilon_2.v$$

$$z_3 = \epsilon_2.u + \epsilon_1.v$$

Finally we have two positiv results :

$$z_{min} = 0,233475630 \times 2.\sqrt{\frac{C}{3}} \quad \text{and}$$

$$z_{max} = 0,725352944 \times 2.\sqrt{\frac{C}{3}}$$

and one negative

$$z_3 = -(z_{max} + z_{min})$$

Then because of $z = \phi^2$

$$\phi_{min} = 0,483193160 \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{4.C}{3}} \quad \text{and}$$

$$\phi_{max} = 0,8516765489 \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{4.C}{3}}$$

In cubic equations the real zeropoints comes from the $\cos(\alpha)$ or from $\sin(90-\alpha)$ of angles (see https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cubic_function).

Then for ϕ_{min} we get an angle α_{min} :

$$\phi_{min} = 0,483193160 \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{4.C}{3}} = \sin(28,894160846) \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{4.C}{3}}$$

$\alpha_{min} = 28,894160846$ degrees is very near to the Weinbergangle

$$\sin^2(\alpha_{min}) = \sin^2(28,894160846) = 0,233475630$$

with Cardanic formular and so on we can express α_{min} by :

$$\boxed{\alpha_{min} = \arcsin\left(\sqrt{-\cos\left(\frac{\arccos\left(\frac{-\sqrt{27}}{8}\right) + \pi}{3}\right)}\right) \approx 28,9^\circ}$$

and for ϕ_{max} we get an angle

$$\phi_{max} = 0,8516765489 \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{4.C}{3}} = \sin(121,605508985) \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{4.C}{3}}$$

$\alpha_{max} = 121,605508985$ degrees

$$\phi_{min} = 0,483193160 \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{4.C}{3}} \approx 0,660464.c \quad \text{c...speed of light}$$

$$\phi_{max} = 0,851676548 \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{4.C}{3}} \approx 1,164134.c$$

In cubic equations the real zeropoints comes from the $\cos(\alpha)$ or from $\sin(90-\alpha)$ of angles (see https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cubic_function).

Geometric interpretation of the roots (zeropoints) in cubic equations with 3 real zeropoints

graphical zeropoints of the derivation of the
(radicalized $\phi^2 = z$) Golden – Potential GP

Hint : On our special Golden – Potential GP the zeropoints (spheres) comes from a pentagon.

< 9 > Conclusions

Dark Energy comes by definition from the Golden – Potential (the second term in the potential).

DarkMatter could be the particles by the SU(5) Symmetry

Some candidates for dark matter are :

1) the $SU(5)$ fermions ($Spin = \frac{1}{2}$) which comes from the fundamental representation.

Not so probable because the exclusion principle would have been observed.

2) the $SU(5)$ vectorbosons ($Spin = 1$) which we have named Gloomons and which comes from the adjoint representation.

Could this be a potential dark matter candidate?

First it is a boson and therefore we have no exclusion principle.

But how do they act together? What happens if different charged Gloomons come near?

We can use the same results as for $SU(3)$. The only difference is that instead of 3 colorcharges we have 5 sensecharges.

Gluons

• $r\bar{r}-g\bar{g}$

○ $\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}(r\bar{r}+g\bar{g}-2b\bar{b})$

Gloomons

Sensecharges = {1, 2, 3, 4, 5} = {See, Touch, Smell, Taste, Hear}

Gloomons = $\left\{ 1\bar{2}, 1\bar{3}, \dots, 4\bar{5}, 1\bar{1} - 2\bar{2}, \dots, \frac{1}{\sqrt{10}}(1\bar{1} + 2\bar{2} + 3\bar{3} + 4\bar{4} - 4.5\bar{5}) \right\}$

• $1\bar{1} - 2\bar{2} \dots$

We assume that they have Planckmass.

We have 24 different types (charging) of Gloomons.

20 of them have nettocharges and 4 have just bruttocharges.

The Gloomons carry charges so they can interact with each other.

The question is how?

We take the gluon self interaction as guide where we have the three-point and the four-point self interactions.

In our model the count of the Gloomons in the universe is fixed (see < 2.1 >).

Therefore a three-point self interaction is not possible.

So only the four-point self interaction left over.

I am using the results from :

<https://doi.org/10.1140/epjc/s10052-020-8260-8>

Four – Point Vertex

$S(2,3,4)$ is the set of permutations of 2, 3, 4. color flow

cannot happen because the count of Gloomons is fixed

Example 1 two identical Gloomons interact

→ attractive

Example 2 two different Gloomons interact

→ repulsive

Why is the force between two identical charged Gloomons attractive?

As seen above only one of the three possibilities left over.

Hence the two Gloomons met in a single point without creating a single Gloomon.

This is like exchanging a spin 2 particle because the two Gloomons have spin 1.

The force between 2 identical charges is attractive by exchanging a spin 2 particle and the force between different charges is repulsive.

Now if the Gloomons are homogene distributed in a Galaxy then the possibility that 2 different charged Gloomons interact is much higher than 2 equal charged Gloomons interact.

Hence we conclude that at all the Gloomons are repulsive distributed in a Galaxy.

Only the Gravitycharge of the Gloomons (they have Planckmass) acts against the repulsive force.

force between two Gloomons

APPENDIX I

Understanding the action of the coxeterement.

As mentioned on the beginning of the paper a coxeterement is a composition of the generating reflections of the reflectiongroup.

In our case the group E_9 (the one point extension of E_8) has 9 such generating reflections $e_1, e_2, e_3, e_4, e_5, e_6, e_7, e_8, e_9$.

A reflection e_i is a reflection on the hyperspace of the root α_i . So the coxeterement is the composition of the rootreflections.

In our case the roots are vectors in the euclidean - space $\mathbb{R}^8$ and the coxeterement is a affine map on this space.

We want to visualize it by the simple example $\tilde{A}_2$

action of $v = s.u.t$ the coxeterement on chamber $C_0 \rightarrow v.C_0$

The action of the coxeterement in this case moves the chamber along the red Line L_v and then reflect it on L_v . Doing the action twice then we move the chamber the double way.

To calculate the eigenvalues and eigenvectors we use the matrix representation of an affine map.

$$\vec{y} = A \cdot \vec{x} + \vec{t} \quad \vec{t} \dots \text{translation vector}$$

This can be written with the augmented matrix

$$\begin{pmatrix} \vec{y} \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} A & \vec{t} \\ 0 \dots 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \vec{x} \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

If we place the origin on the red vertical translation line then the affine map is :

$$\begin{pmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{matrix} \text{reflection} \\ \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \end{matrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{matrix} \text{translation} \\ \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \sqrt{3} \end{pmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

Then the augmented representation is

$$\begin{pmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & \sqrt{3} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

The characteristic polynomial the coxeter polynomial then is

$$P(\lambda) = -(\lambda + 1) \cdot (\lambda - 1)^2 = -\frac{\lambda^2 - 1}{\lambda - 1} \cdot (\lambda - 1)^2$$

eigenvalues $\lambda_h = -1, \lambda_v = 1, \lambda_t = 1$
eigenvectors $v_h \quad v_v \quad v_t$

$\lambda_h = -1$ is the eigenvalue by this cyclotomic factor and is the eigenvalue of the so called horizontal root(system). This produces the reflection on the red line.

$\lambda_v = 1$ is one eigenvalue of this factor and is the eigenvalue of the so called vertical root(system). Vertical because the root is orthogonal to the horizontal root(system).

$\lambda_t = 1$ is one eigenvalue of this factor and produces the translation on the red line.

With the eigenvector v_h which will be reflected by the coxeter element action we have a simple root for the Lie algebra $\mathfrak{su}(2)$.

And with the eigenvectors v_v and v_t we have roots for $\mathfrak{u}(1)$.

So in summary the coxeter element generates the Symmetry

$$SU(2) \times U(1) \times E(1)$$

Analogous for E_9 which is $\tilde{E}_8$ the coxeter element generates the symmetric composition $SU(5) \times SU(3) \times SU(2) \times U(1) \times E(1)$.

We see that in case of $\tilde{A}_2$ the translation is not of integer type this means the coordinates for the translation vector can not be written all as integers. How does this look for the affine map by the coxeter element of the affine coxeter group $E_9 = \tilde{E}_8$?

What is the translation vector for E_9 ?

First we want to give the simple roots for E_9 .

$$\Phi = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ -1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ -1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ -1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ -1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} -1 \\ 1 \\ -1 \\ -1 \\ -1 \\ -1 \\ -1 \\ -1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}, \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} -1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \\ -1 \\ -1 \\ -1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \\ -1 \end{pmatrix} \right\}$$

The length of the simple roots is the same and is chosen for $\sqrt{2} \Rightarrow E_9$ is selfdual.

Then the Coxeter - Axis direction is

$$L_v = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \\ 3 \\ -3 \\ 2 \\ 2 \end{pmatrix}$$

see <https://arxiv.org/abs/1312.7777> Example 11.8

The coxeterement of E_9 is doing 9 reflections $v = r_1.r_2.r_3.r_4.r_5.r_6.r_7.r_8.r_9$

The reflections r_i are defined by the reflections on the hyperplane of the simple roots α_i of E_9 .

As we have seen in our example A_2 the coxeterement produces a glider reflection

along the coxeter axis L_v (reflection $\perp L_v$ and translation along L_v).

Similar the coxeterement of E_9 produces

- 1) a reflection $\perp L_v$.
- 2) a rotation by $\frac{2\pi}{3} \perp L_v$ which comes from 2 reflections.
- 3) a "double" rotation by $\frac{2\pi}{5} \perp L_v$ which comes from 4 reflections.
- 4) a translation along the coxeter axis L_v .

schematic presentation

Important hint!

The generator of the hypercharge is totally different to the generator of the gravity because in case of gravity it is a translation and in case of hypercharge not!

Hint!

Doing the action of the coxeterement v 30 times which is v^{30} then the action is just a translation along L_v .

$30 = 2.3.5 = \text{coxeternumber of } A_1 \times A_2 \times A_4$.

The simple roots for the groups A_1, A_2 and A_4 are :

$$\underline{A_1} : \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad \underline{A_2} : \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} ; \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \\ -1 \\ -1 \\ -1 \\ -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad \underline{A_4} : \begin{pmatrix} -1 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} ; \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} ; \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ -1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} ; \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} -1 \\ 1 \\ -1 \\ -1 \\ 1 \\ -1 \\ -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

We have the eigenvalue 1 twice (algebraic multiplicity = 2) in the characteristic polynomial of the coxeter element map.
The geometrical multiplicity to this eigenvalue is 1.

APPENDIX II

Our target is to show that

$$\Lambda_p l_p^2 = \frac{16}{\varphi} \cdot N^2 = \frac{16}{\varphi} \cdot \left(\frac{\sqrt{\varphi}}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{48!} \right)^2 = \frac{4}{48!^2} \approx \frac{2,6}{10^{122}} \quad \varphi \dots \text{golden ratio}$$

For that we start with the Combinatorial – Form and going back to the Einstein – Form of the Golden – Potential GP

On the combinatorial form we have set $c = h = G = 1$.

$$V(\phi) = N^4 \cdot \left(-8 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^2 + 16 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^4 - 8 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^8 \right) \quad \boxed{N = \frac{\sqrt{\varphi}}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{48!}}$$

We will take this back and get

$$V(\phi) = \left(\frac{P_p}{2\pi} \right)^2 \cdot N^4 \cdot \left(-8 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{c\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^2 + 16 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{c\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^4 - 8 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{c\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^8 \right)$$

With the relation

$$P_p l_p^2 = \frac{c^4}{G}$$

we get

$$V(\phi) = \left(\frac{c^4}{2\pi G} \cdot \frac{1}{l_p^2} \right)^2 \cdot N^4 \cdot \left(-8 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{c\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^2 + 16 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{c\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^4 - 8 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{c\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^8 \right) \quad \left| \cdot \frac{\Lambda^2}{\Lambda^2} \right.$$

Then

$$V(\phi) = \left(\frac{\Lambda c^4}{2\pi G} \cdot \frac{1}{\Lambda l_p^2} \right)^2 \cdot N^4 \cdot \left(-8 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{c\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^2 + 16 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{c\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^4 - 8 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{c\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^8 \right) \quad \left| \cdot \frac{\varphi^2}{\varphi^2} \cdot \frac{4^2}{4^2} \right.$$

Then

$$V(\phi) = \left(\frac{\Lambda c^4}{8\pi G} \right)^2 \cdot \left(\frac{4^2}{\Lambda l_p^2 \varphi} \right)^2 \cdot N^4 \cdot \left(-\frac{\varphi}{2} \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{c} \right|^2 + \left| \frac{\phi}{c} \right|^4 - \frac{1}{2 \cdot \varphi^2} \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{c} \right|^8 \right)$$

Comparing with the Einstein – Form this must be 1.

Then

$$\boxed{\Lambda_p l_p^2 = \frac{4}{48!^2}}$$

QED.

